

Erratum

Kinetics of palladium(II)-catalyzed oxidation of sulfur(IV) by oxygen

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p. 1038, column 2, last para :

'The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{II} , for second path did not depend on pH, [buffer], [O₂], [chloride] and [S^{IV}]'

should be read as

"The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{II} , for second path did not depend on pH, [buffer], [O₂] and [chloride] but depended on [S^{IV}] as shown in Table 2"

p. 1040, column 1, top :

'Scheme 1 : $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_n]^{(2n-2)-} + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_1 \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_3$ '

should be read as

" $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_n]^{(2n-2)-} + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_1 \xrightleftharpoons{\text{SO}_3^{2-}} \text{C}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_3$ " and the subsequent discussion accordingly.

